

Project VULCANO

DEVELOPEMENT OF BASIC TECHNOLOGIES FOR THE PRODUCTION OF METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This project aims to develop **basic technologies** for the manufacture of **METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES** with major possibilities of **industrial application**.

The production technologies dealt with in this project are :

Squeeze casting
Rheocasting
Compocasting
Forging
Low pressure metal infiltration
Powder metallurgy

Several **systems** are undergoing research: Al & Mg alloy matrixes, reinforced with short fibers, continuous monofilament fibers, particles or whiskers. The combination of matrix ductility with the rigidity and resistance due to the reinforcements results in the **characteristic advantages** of these materials: a) **greater wear resistance**, b) **dimensional stability** (less thermal dilatation), c) **maintainment of mechanical traits** at high temperatures, and d) ameliorated properties without a significant increase in weight .

The development of the **tools** necessary for the **design & calculation** of MMC products & their uses is planned, also the **manufacture & testing** of diverse demonstration **prototypes** for the **application** of these materials in the **automobile , military & aerospace** fields of industry. Ample possibilities of other use, such as electronics, sports, recreation, etc. are foreseen in the near future.

Finally, the project VULCANO includes a **complete characterization** of the materials obtained, the **behavior** of the **prototypes** produced, and the development of **Non-destructive Testing** techniques adapted to these materials.

1. Objectives

The main objective is to gain knowledge of the basic production techniques with mayor industrial interest for the obtaining of a series of MMC's, by way of different technologies, duly analyzed and characterized in relation to their corresponding advantages, faults and possibilities of application. The goal of this project is to produce and test prototypes that would show the advantages of these materials in the fields of the automobile, military and aerospace industries, though use is foreseen in other sectors such as sports, electronics, recreation, etc.

More precisely, a rod and piston for use in automobiles, an isostatic platform component for the aerospace industry, and a SABOT for anti-armored car projectile launcher for military use.

2. A Multi-company Project

The realization of a project of the magnitude of VULCANO is only feasible through the joint participation of several companies that pool their resources and efforts to in order to reach a common goal. Multi-company cooperation is a strongly established tendency in the world today, and is accepted as one of the key factors in competitiveness. Knowing this, the INI Group (National Institute of Industry) gave start to the initiative of this Project, and from this point formed a work group, coordinated by a new company within INI, TGI (currently forming part of TENE0), and consisting of the following companies:

In the production area :

INESPAL (Empresa Española del Aluminio,S.A.)

FOARSA (Forjas y Aceros, S.A.)

TGI (Tecnología y Gestión de la Innovación)

As possible future users of materials developed :

Empresa Nacional Santa Barbara

CASA (Construcciones Aeronauticas S.A.)

ENOSA (Industria Nacional de Optica)

Investigation Centers that supply technological support :

CENIM (Centro Nacional de Investigaciones Metalurgicas)

ETSICCIP (Escuela Tecnica Superior de Ingenieros de Caminos,Canales y Puertos)

INASMET (Centro Tecnologico de Materiales)

This project has the financial support of the Technological and Industrial Development Center of the Ministry of Industry, Commerce and Tourism. It was given start on the 1st of January 1991, and will be completed in a 36 month period. The budget reaches 470 million pesetas, and there are more than 40 research scientists involved.

3. Advantages

The main advantages of MMC's over conventional materials are :

- Ameliorated properties without a significant increase in weight, thanks to the addition of ceramic reinforcements in the metallic matrixes.
- Higher wear resistance, due to specific reinforcements in the matrix, that make this material extraordinarily suitable for the production of motor components.
- Dimensional stability in the face of temperature changes: a low Thermal Expansion Coefficient (TEC), because of the addition of long directional fibers, that convert MMC's into materials that are particularly useful for certain applications, for example in aerospace construction.
- Mechanical properties maintained at high temperatures, a "sin qua non" in motor components.

4. Project Phases

In order to optimize the carrying out, VULCANO has been divided into the following phases :

- Bibliographical study of the technique, in relation to production technology, materials systems, non-destructive testing technologies, etc.
- Selection of materials systems in accordance with the objectives planned.
- Definition of applications, followed by a demonstration of the advantages of MMC's.
- Calculus and design.
- Preforming Technologies.
- Production Technologies to be developed during the project :
 - * Forming these materials through forging.
 - * Low pressure infiltration
 - * Compcasting: Shaking of the matrix and reinforcement when in a liquid or semiliquid state, at a determined temperature.
 - * Powder metallurgy: pressure and temperature treatment (lower than melting point) of metallic powder, blended with the reinforcing material, in order to obtain a compact mass.
 - * Squeeze casting.
- Characterization according to objectives and foreseen applications.
- Production of prototypes.
- Study of prototype behavior.
- Development of non-destructive testing technology specially for these materials.

Figure 1
A SCHEMATIC DRAWING OF THE COMOCASTING PROCESS

Figure 2
MATERIAL OBTAINED BY THE COMOCASTING PROCESS (Al-Si ALLOY WITH SiC_p REINFORCEMENT)

Figure 3

MICROGRAPH OF MAGNESIUM INFILTRATION INTO A C-FIBER PREFORM. AZ91/COMPOSITE MICROSTRUCTURE, WHERE A SMALL ZONE OF "PULL OUT" CAN BE OBSERVED. (DEVELOPEMENT OF Mg/C COMPOSITES FOR THE SABBOT PROTOTYPE)

Figure 4

MICROGRAPH OF MAGNESIUM INFILTRATION INTO A C-FIBER PREFORM. AZ91/COMPOSITE MICROSTRUCTURE, WHERE GOOD FIBER DISTRIBUTION & CONSIDERABLE PLASTIC DEFORMATION OF THE MATRIX CAN BE OBSERVED. (DEVELOPEMENT OF Mg/C COMPOSITES FOR THE SABBOT PROTOTYPE)

Figure 5

HOMOGENOUS DISTRIBUTION OF SiCp PARTICLES IN Al MATRIX.
MATERIAL OBTAINED BY POWDERMETALLURGY. (MECHANICAL MIXING OF
ALUMINUM ALLOY WITH SiCp PARTICLES FOLLOWED BY EXTRUSION).

Figure 6

THE FIRST PISTON PROTOTYPE OBTAINED BY SQUEEZE CASTING